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SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN INDIA: ISSUES AND CHALLENGES

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ABSTRACT

Inclusive education is not a opportunity it is child's right. In India there are many children who are out of the school .So Inclusive education is really excellent approach in the field of education system because it gives the education to children with special needs. Sustainable growth in the view of Inclusive education system is very important in the present situation because Sustainable development that assembles the need of the present without including the capacity of the future age band to meet their own needs. Government of India, gave importance to Inclusive Education system, in its course of action, planned several steps for the sustainable development of Inclusive education system in India. This study exposes the issues and challenges faced by the Inclusive Education and suggest the measures for implementing and improving the Inclusive education. To make sure that Government services are beneficial for the sustainable development of the Inclusive Education and also to study the significance of sustainable development in the field of Inclusive Education by using the secondary data.

Keywords: Sustainable development, Inclusive education.

Introduction

According to U-DISE 2016-17 data, about 19.6% of students belong to SC at the primary school level, but this fraction falls to 17.3% at the higher secondary level. These enrolment drop-offs are even more severe for ST students (10.6% to 6.8%), Muslim students (15% to 7.9%), and differently-able children (1.1% to 0.25%), with even greater declines for female students within each of these URG. The declines in enrolment of higher education are even steeper. While different educational policies have attempted to reach out to these previously excluded children, those with disabilities are often

forgotten, emphasizing their invisible status in a rigidly categorized society. Therefore Inclusive education is extremely good strategy in the field of education system for special children. While inclusive education has its benefits there are huge challenge get in the way of effective implementation especially in India.

Objectives of the study

1. To find out the issues and challenges faced by the Inclusive Education System.
2. To suggest the measures for implementing and improving the Inclusive Education.
3. To analyze provided Government facilities are beneficial for the sustainable development of the Inclusive Education.
4. To study the significance of sustainable development in the field of Inclusive Education by using the secondary data.

Methodology for the study

Research methodology is the systematic way to solve the research problem. The study undertaken includes secondary data and descriptive method was followed.

Concept of Study

Inclusive Education: Inclusive education is about integration approach of special children in schools. In this system the learners with special needs spend most of the time with non-disabled learners. They enjoy field trips, school activities and attend the same sports meet and play together. It values the diversity and unique contribution of each student brings to classroom. In a real inclusive setting every child feels safe and has sense of belonging. It is a process of addressing and responding to diversity of needs of all children, youth and adults through increasing participation in learning ,cultures and communities , reducing and eliminating exclusion from within and from education (UNESCO,1994).

Sustainable Development

As per the Bruntland report “Sustainable development that meets the need of the present without comprising the ability of the future generation to meet their own needs. It has three main pillars economic, environmental and social these three pillars are informally referred to as people planet and profit.

Sustainable Development in Inclusive Education

Education is the greatest tool for attaining social justice and equality. The Ministry of Welfare, now Social Justice and Empowerment, implemented the Integrated Education for Disabled Children (IEDC) scheme from 1974 to 1982,(Dasgupta, 2002). The proposal was apparently intended to encourage co-operation between conventional and special schools in order to support integration, In 1987, UNICEF and the government-funded National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT) launched the Project on Integrated Education for Disabled (PIED) in 10 blocks (the administrative level between district and village (Thomas, 2005b)), that focused on teacher training in order to encourage integration, Mahila Samakhya Program started in 1989 is program designed promote education and empowerment of women in rural areas particularly those from the socially and economically marginalized, The 1995 District Primary Education Programme (DPEP), funded 85% by Central government via a World Bank loan and support from the European Community, UNICEF and the UK and Netherlands governments, and 15% by the State governments, focused on the universalisation of primary education, particularly for girls. The intention was for district-specific planning to make the programme contextual, and for participatory processes to empower and build capacity at all levels (GOI, 2002). Janshala

This community schools programme, started in 1998 and now replaced by SSA, was collaboration between the Government of India and the UNDP, UNICEF, UNESCO, the ILO, and UNFPA, and supported the government drive towards universal primary education. It covered 120, mainly rural, blocks in 9 States where there is evidence of low female literacy, child labor, and SC/ST children not catered for under DPEP (Mukhopadhyay, 2005). Unfortunately, due to limited availability of data, it is not possible to elaborate on any issues arising on the Janshala programme, which has a component designed to improve the attendance of difficult to reach groups of children, including children with disabilities. Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA) is the government's millennial Education For All umbrella programme for all education schemes, which aims to universalize elementary education. The goals are that all children aged 6-14 i) will be in some form of education by 2003, ii) will complete 5 years' primary education by 2007, and iii) will complete 8 years' education by 2010 (GOI, 2002). Disability indicators are included in the government agreement for SSA (Thomas, 2005a), although what exactly these are and whether they are taken on at local level is unclear. The Right of children to Free and compulsory Education Act 2009, which represents every child of age of six to fourteen years with the right to free and compulsory education in a neighborhood school till completion of elementary education.

Issues and challenges

Inclusive Education has its own set of challenges, some of which are very serious and impeding. Following are the some of the main problems that India faces in the field of inclusive education system.

- Negative Attitude towards special children result in discrimination and lead to a serious barrier to learning. It takes form of social inequity, lack of comprehension and traditional discrimination .In some province it is believed that educating special children is futile. The problem is identified as being caused by child's indifferences rather than educations deficiency.
- Curriculum is one of the major obstacles to facilitate the development of inclusive system. Curriculum is often unable to meet the needs or wide range of different learners. In several contexts the core curriculum is centrally designed and unbending leaving little flexibility for native variations for educators to experiment and check out new approaches.
- Teaching and learning often takes place through a language which is difficult to grasp for the special children .In this case learners often lead to linguistic difficulties which contribute to learning breakdown.
- The majority educational institutions are physically inaccessible to many learners especially those who have physical disabilities. In poorer area the centers of learning are often in accessible largely because buildings are run down or feebly maintained. They are unhealthy and insecure for all the learners. Many schools are characterized by inadequacy facilities to respond to special needs such as classrooms, furniture's, doors, passage, stairs and ramps are the main problems identified by many students .This limits the enrollment of special children in the regular schools.
- Inadequacies and inequalities in the education system are most evident in areas which have sustained poverty and high levels of unemployment.
- Teaching aids are very important in teaching the learners in inclusive classroom. Since the good presentation should comprise all the essential tools which help the learners understand the lesson well. Inadequate teaching resources make it hard for the teachers to deliver the materials and for the learners.
- Large number of student-teacher ratio is the challenge that teachers face in implementation of inclusive education. Here the educator complains that they have many students in the class who needs support but teachers cannot manage all of them.

Suggestions

- Making sure that educator have the guidance flexibility and resources to teach students with diverse needs and learning styles.

- Proficient use of information and communication for improving access to Inclusive education, enhancing the teaching- learning process, training of teachers and strengthening educational planning and management.
- Clear and efficient possibility for obtaining financial support should be provided to schools or school complexes for integration of special children, as well as for the establishment of resource centers at the village/block level where needed for learners with severe or multiple disabilities - such centers would assist parents/guardians in part-time or full time home-schooling and in skilling such learners.
- School syllabi, curriculum, and teaching learning materials (especially textbooks) should be reviewed to identify and remove overt or hidden bias and stereotyping.
- Student-Teacher Ratio in schools with a high proportion of learners should not be extra than 25:1. Thus keeping the percentage in brain the corrective measures and bridge activities that will be required at every such school on a continuous basis until such time that the gaps are bridged.

Conclusion

Inclusive education is changing from phenomenological perspective here the stakeholders driven and influenced not straightforward and a long term journey or process of conflict rather than the outline. There is necessity to sustain the development in the inclusive education in India. But numerous time our government guarantee all necessary help to inclusive education sadly most of it remains only on document. Therefore the fundamental Right of Education for all children as declared by 86th constitutional amendment in 2002 may possibly be fulfilled in long term through improved implementation of inclusive education. Therefore laborious effort is being made to give confidence the stakeholders of inclusive education.

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